

STORABLE NEWSLETTER

Dear reader,

Some months have passed by since the first STORABLE newsletter. A busy period to consolidate our cluster and to work on the advice given by our mentors from the Booster program.

Final NeoGiANT event

Our parent project, the Horizon 2020 NeoGiANT (<https://neogiant.eu>), held its final event in Santiago de Compostela (Spain) in March. This activity combined open presentations of the project's achievements with leisure activities to celebrate not only the scientific and practical findings but also the new opportunities and friendship NeoGiANT has enabled.

This event marks the end of four and a half exciting years, and the results are still being released. The experience and knowledge treasured in this project are inspiring for the PhD candidates in STORABLE.

Some prototypes developed in the NeoGiANT project.

First journal club

The journal club activity was suggested in the Booster sessions as a way to diversify our activities while focusing on the young researchers in the cluster. Devised as an activity managed by researchers in their first career stages, we invited pre- and junior post-docs to participate.

In this first session, Ms. **Nayana Shetty** from BullNet MSCA DN

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(University of Nottingham) moderated the activity, and Mr. **Adrián Martín-San-Juan** presented and discussed the publication:

Jakop, U., Engel, K. M., Hürland, M., Müller, P., Osmers, J.-H., Jung, M., & Schulze, M. (2023). Lipid alterations by oxidative stress increase detached acrosomes after cryopreservation of semen in Holstein bulls.

Theriogenology, 197, 37–45.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2022.11.036>

This was a very stimulating and encouraging activity, and we plan to hold it bimonthly. The next session is programmed for the summer, with Ms. Nayana Shetty as presenter.

STORABLE in Zenodo and YouTube

To increase dissemination of the cluster's activities, we have been sharing its outputs on the Open Science platform Zenodo. We have created the STORABLE community to upload material produced within the cluster: recordings of meetings, presentations, newsletters, and other materials. You are free to download, share, and use the videos and documents there. Just click the link:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/nogiant-storable/>

Moreover, we have shared the videos on YouTube for wider diffusion. Here is a list of the full collection of recordings from our online activities:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iySWvbN-cl&list=PLzL6onEh8d1GCmE2yCtWf8Ne3tr_gKJF1

Horizon Results Booster program

STORABLE receives ongoing support from the Booster program (<https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>). Through a series of services

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(aimed at dissemination and results exploitation). Their help has significantly improved STORABLE's activities, providing excellent ideas and ways to advance its objectives.

Next steps

STORABLE is organizing a new webinar, the next one in the "Eco-ART: A Webinar Series on Sustainable Sperm Storage and Reproductive Biotechnologies in Animal Science."

UPCOMING EVENTS

By June-July, this event will focus on solutions developed by companies in animal reproduction, leading to improved sustainability in animal breeding. We expect at least three experts from international companies to discuss novel products and strategies, so stay tuned!

The next Journal Club will take place soon too. In several weeks, Mr. Adrián Martín-San-Juan will announce this session, which will provide another great opportunity for learning about new developments in animal

reproduction technologies and sustainability.

Acknowledgments and contacts

The coordinators warmly thank all the partners for their excellent disposition. We include the NeoGiANT project, the Horizon 2020 program, and the Booster program from Horizon Europe for their support.

If you want to know more about STORABLE's partners or contact them, you can find them at:

<https://bianorbiotech.es/>

<https://www.jcu.cz/en/>

<https://www.vri.cz/en/900-2/>

<https://magapor.com/>

<https://www.ul.ie/research/bullnet-research>

<https://precisioncelular.com/>

<https://www.cryostoreproject.com/>

<https://semencardona.com/>

<https://veterinaria.ucm.es/conerepro>

<https://aimiberica.com/>

<https://topignorsvin.com/>

<https://www.inia.es/en-en/Research/Animalresearch/animalreproduction/Spermatology%20in%20Animal%20Production%20and%20Conservation/Paginas/Home.aspx>

You can follow STORABLE's news and activities at [LinkedIn](#), [Bluesky](#), and [Mastodon](#).